

Assessment on availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of Literature-in-English among secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja

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Abstracts

This study assessed the availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of Literature-in-English among secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja. Three specific objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and a four-point scale model of questionnaire was used as research instrument. The population of the study comprised 915 Art students and 22 English Language teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada Area Council. The sample size of 292 respondents was drawn using simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques using an intact class. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.89 was obtained using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient which implies the instrument is reliable. The method of data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages and mean scores for the research questions and demographic data. The hypotheses were tested using the t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis showed that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada [$t_{\text{value}} = 1.413$, $df = 290$, $P < 0.05$]; there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada [$t_{\text{value}} = 0.641$, $df = 290$, $P > 0.05$]; there was a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada [$t_{\text{value}} = 2.694$, $df = 290$, $P > 0.05$]. The research concluded that teachers need support to effectively utilize the available instructional facilities to enhance the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English thereby boosting students' understanding and performance in the subject. Based on the findings, it is recommended among others that: more instructional facilities should be made available and accessible to schools so that teachers would utilize them frequently and they should be trained to utilize such resources to support their efficiency.

Keywords: Availability, utilization, instructional materials, curriculum and Literature-in-English

Introduction

Education is said to be the process through which experienced and knowledgeable members of the society (teachers) impart knowledge into the inexperienced learners so as to develop their skills. This teaching and learning process occurs or takes place in varying ways and in different places. In an informal educational sitting, the teaching and learning process could take place in a workshop, on the farm, or in any place where learners are taught practical lessons. Ogbuanya and Okoye, 2015 noted that this practical-oriented teaching and learning process often results in a more fruitful way especially when the objective is to acquire or develop skills. In the realm of formal education, however, the classroom is the main or primary theatre where teaching and learning operations take place. The ideas and skills taught are presented in forms of lessons in the classroom.

Uchechi (2021) noted that this form of learning often leads to the acquisition of abstract knowledge and ideas which the learner may not be able to apply them outside the classroom. This underscores the importance of having a real-time experience in the teaching and learning process. Learning outside the classroom is vital to students' understanding and appreciation of the real-world phenomena. Because the concepts and ideas taught in the classroom exists in the real world around us, and learners may better understand and appreciate them when they have an experience of the real situations or contexts outside the classroom, teachers often try to recreate this existential reality by bringing into the classroom, materials and other resources that may give the learners these experiences that they need to master the ideas and concepts taught. The teacher may sometimes too, decide to take the students outside the classroom to learn about certain things that may not be authentically recreated in the classroom.

Language and literature where the learning points (concepts and ideas) are largely abstract, connecting with the real world situation, not only make learning real and meaningful but also helps the learner to better appreciate what is taught or learned. Learning barriers caused by the abstract nature of language and literature dissolve as learners connect with and learn

from their environment, (Kouider and Mohammed (2019). Literature, essentially, is said to be a reflection of the society because it mirrors the culture and activities of the people in a particular society. Hence, the best way to teach and understand literary concepts and texts might be to connect with the social situations in the society which literary text mirrors. In other words, to teach students about the culture and activities of a particular people as reflected in a literary text, it makes more sense to engage and connect them with the people whose culture they are being taught. For example, imagine the interactions that occur among students and the teacher when they visit a museum which exhibits the cultural artefacts discussed in a literary text they are studying. Such a visit offers them the opportunity to talk about what they have read in a text and are now seeing. It becomes easier to relate with what they are seeing in the museum (a phenomenon outside the classroom) to what they have learned or read in a text. Such a visit gives them the opportunity to experience and better appreciate what they have learnt in the classroom.

Jason, Gregor, Lori, Amael and Mariya (2018) opined that social discourse and direct experience help learners to better construct an understanding of literary phenomena. Certainly, learners will better appreciate and understand an aspect of a culture when they interact with the people who practice it. This explains the invaluable benefits of instructional facilities to teaching and learning generally, and to literature in particular. They believed that the use of these resources for teaching and learning creates a lasting memory and enduring learning experience for the learner. Certainly, the use of instructional facilities in teaching can make students appreciate the local and international relevance of what they learn in schools while affording them the opportunity to apply literary concepts and theories in appropriate social contexts. This is supported by Weipeng and Hui (2020), who, in her study on the development of localised instructional resources in Hong Kong, came to the conclusion that teaching and learning of humanities and social Literature-in-English subjects could be enhanced to a greater extent by using instructional resources within local contexts since such resources are often considered to be authentic and relevant to students' learning needs. Indeed, researchers have held the view that the use of instructional facilities in teaching and learning allow students to experience and discover answers to issues for themselves. This means the use of instructional facilities promote active learning that engages the learners in the process.

Furthermore, importance of instructional facilities for teaching literature in secondary schools and, indeed, at all levels of education has been well noted by scholars. Apart from enhancing the quality of teaching and learning, it is well known that the use tends to improve students' retention abilities which leads to improved academic performance/achievement since it makes learning real, authentic and more concrete Abdirahman, Willy and Mohammed, (2018). Although the use of instructional facilities can enhance teaching and learning in the classroom, the realisation of their full potential to motivate and engage students may be limited, partly because of the readiness of the teachers to use them. This is probably because some of them (the teachers) might not have acquired the skills and capacities to use the resources. As it is the case with all instructional facilities, improvisation is a major task which demands skills and expertise by the teacher since not all potentially good resources can be effectively utilized for actual classroom teaching.

Another major challenge that seems to plague the successful use of community resources for teaching literature in Nigerian secondary schools generally, and Gwagwalada in particular, is the unavailability of funds to plan and sponsor such outdoor trips for learning. When the funds to sponsor the students' trip to particular community resource centre like a museum are not readily available, there is nothing a teacher can do no matter how skilled and enthusiastic he/she might about using such resources.

Instructional facilities that can enhance the learning of literature include physical features (like settlements, shrines, museums, mountains, river, coastal areas, desert areas and forest); human activities (that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, among others); and people in various communities (like religious leaders likes chief priests, pastors, imams, community leaders like traditional rulers or government officials) Dzekoto and Daryl (2018). These should always be exploited and utilised by literature teachers to enrich the learning experiences of their students. Since the contents of literary texts reflect issues that have to do with these cultural or community features and members, when students engage with them, they tend to understand them better. This highlights the relevance of instructional facilities to the teaching or implementation of Literature-in-English curriculum. Hence, this study assessed the availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of literature-in-English among secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja.

Objectives of the Study

1. To ascertain the availability of instructional facilities for the teaching of Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja;
2. To determine the level of utilisation of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja;

3. To examine the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja.

Research Questions

1. What are the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?
2. What are the levels of utilisation of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?
3. What are the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for this research consisted of all students in the Arts classes who offer Literature-in-English and all teachers who teach English language and Literature-in-English in the public Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja. The total number of Arts students who offer Literature-in-English students in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada, based on the enrolment records for 2019/2020 academic session is nine hundred and fifteen (915). The number of English language and Literature-in-English teachers in various schools were twenty-two (22). The sample was drawn from all the eight public Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for sample size determination. The purposive sampling method and simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 270 respondents were drawn from target population.

The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire titled, "Assessment of the relevance of instructional materials for teaching Literature-in-English in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ARCRTLSSQ)". This was developed by the researcher and used for the purpose of eliciting the responses of students and teachers on the issue investigated. The questionnaire was a four-point scale model with two parts. Part A sought to elicit the respondents' demographic data, particularly their designated status (students or teachers). This constituted a categorical variable for the analysis of the hypotheses. Part B elicited respondents' responses with regard to the five issues raised by the research questions. This entails that part B of the questionnaire has five sections numbered 1 to 5 with forty (40) items numbered as follow: research question one, 1-10; research question two, 11-20; research question three, 21-30; research question four, 31-35; and research question five, 36-40. Responses to each item were graded on the scale of: Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1; Very Great Extent (VGE) = 4, Great Extent (GE) = 3, Small Extent (SE) = 2, Very Small Extent (VSE) = 1; and Always (A) = 4, Often (O) = 3, Sometimes (S) = 2, and Never (N) = 1. To determine the validity of the instrument, face validation by experts in the Department of English Language, University of Abuja; and two Biology teachers from sampled senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja. The reliability status of the instrument gave an index of 0.89 using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (PPMC). Analysis of data was carried out using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages and mean scores for the research questions and demographic data. For the four-point scale, the decision rule was the midpoint of 2.50. Thus, mean scores equal to or above 2.50 signified agreements while those below 2.50 were taken to mean disagreement respectively.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Demographic Data of the of Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage %
Teachers	22	8%
Students	270	92%
Total	292	100%

As shown in Table 1, there are total of 292 valid respondents with total of 22 respondents representing 8% of the sample were teachers while the students were 270 representing 92% of the sample.

Research Question 1

What are the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Table 2: The Availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada: N=292

Available instructional facilities	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean	Decision
Settlements	153	38	60	41	3.04	Agreed
Shrines	42	36	119	95	2.09	Disagreed
Museums	0	0	0	292	1.00	Disagreed
Theatre centres	10	65	130	87	1.99	Disagreed
Industrial centres such as workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc	202	63	21	06	3.58	Agreed
Market centres	200	64	22	06	3.57	Agreed
Worship centres such as churches, mosque, Buddhist temple, etc	212	70	10	0	3.69	agreed
Other significant physical features like rivers, mountains, etc	190	70	29	03	3.53	Agreed
Human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc	150	71	61	10	3.24	Agreed
Human resources (significant personalities in various communities such as religious leaders (like chief priests, pastors, imams); community leaders (like traditional rulers, government officials, etc); farmers; artists, etc)	209	63	19	01	3.64	Agreed
2.94						Agreed

The data in Table 2 above presents the analysis of respondents' responses with regard to determining the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada. Based on the analysis of mean scores for each item, the respondents agreed that the following instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English are available: settlements (3.04), market centres (3.57) and industrial centres (such as workshops, blacksmith or farms) (3.58). They also agreed that worship centres (church/mosque, Buddhist temple) and physical features such as (rivers or mountains) are available in their communities as indicated by the mean scores of 3.69 and 3.53 respectively. Others include the human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc. (3.24) and human resources (significant personalities like community leaders, religious leaders, artists, farmers) that could be utilized to facilitate the teaching of Literature-in-English in their schools (3.64).

The cumulative computation of mean scores recorded for individual items under this research question yielded the sectional mean of 2.94 which indicates agreement, having been higher than the 2.50 decision rule. This serves to indicate the respondents have accepted that the instructional facilities listed above was available for the purpose of teaching and learning Literature-in-English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Research Question 2

What are the levels of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Table 3: Level of Utilization of the Available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada: N=292

ITEM	A (4)	O (3)	S (2)	N (1)	Mean	Decision
A visit to the local settlements	20	15	117	140	1.71	Sometimes
A visit to the shrine	0	0	101	191	1.35	Never

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A visit to the museum	0	0	120	172	1.41	Never
A visit to the Theatre centres	01	23	117	151	1.57	Sometimes
A visit to industrial centres including workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc.	04	28	154	106	1.76	Sometimes
A visit to market centres	0	0	204	88	1.70	Sometimes
A visit to a worship center (such as the church/mosque, Buddhist temple)	0	18	166	108	1.75	Sometimes
A visit to other significant physical features like rivers, mountains, etc.	22	01	167	102	1.80	Sometimes
An excursion to observe significant human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc.	12	08	207	65	1.89	Sometimes
Interaction with significant personalities in the local community such as religious leaders (like chief priests, pastors, imams); community leaders (like traditional rulers, government officials, etc); farmers; artists, etc	18	0	166	108	1.75	Sometimes

1.67 Sometimes

Table 3 above presents the analysis of respondents' responses to determine the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada. The result of the analysis as shown the table indicates that the English language teachers utilized the following instructional facilities to teach Literature-in-English sometimes: local settlements (1.71), theatre centres (1.57), industrial centres including workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc. (1.76) and market centres (1.70). Sometimes too, they utilized worship centres (1.75), physical features like mountains, rivers, (1.80), human activities (1.89) and resource persons (1.75). Given that the sectional mean of 1.67 is far below the decision rule of 2.50, the study concludes that the available instructional facilities are only used sometimes to teach and learn Literature-in-English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada. Therefore, the current level of their utilization is poor.

Research Question 3

What are the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Table 6: Extent of Respondents' Perception of relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada. N=292

ITEM	VGE (4)	GE (3)	SE (2)	VSE (1)	Mean	Decision
Settlements	225	59	08	0	3.74	VGE
Shrines	37	37	124	94	2.06	SE
Museums	158	86	36	12	3.34	GE
Theatre centres	200	75	15	02	3.62	VGE
Industrial centres including workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc	163	90	27	12	3.38	GE
Market centres	168	78	32	14	3.37	GE
Worship centres (church/mosque, Buddhist temple)	209	63	01	0	3.64	VGE
Other significant physical features like rivers, mountains, etc	225	59	08	0	3.74	VGE
Human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc.	200	75	15	02	3.62	VGE

Human resources i.e. significant personalities in various communities such as religious leaders (like chief priests, pastors, imams); community leaders (like traditional rulers, government officials, etc); farmers; artists, etc	168	88	24	12	3.41	GE
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3.39 GE

Table 6 above presents the analysis of respondents’ responses so as to determine the extent to which the use of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools is relevant for improving students’ understanding of the subject. The sectional mean score of 3.39 which the analysis yielded is above the decision rule of 2.50, and falls with the mean score range of ‘to a great extent’. On this basis, the study concludes that the respondents perceived that the use of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools is relevant for improving students’ understanding of the subject to a great extent.

Hypotheses

H₀₁ : There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Table 9: Result of t-test Analysis on the difference between Respondents’ Perceptions of the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada

Designation	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Teacher	22	3.01	0.21	1.413	290	0.159	Accepted
Student	270	2.93	0.27				

P-Value of 0.159 > 0.05

The analysis shown in Table 9 was computed to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada or not. The result shows a significant value of 0.159 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance set as the decision rule. Consequently, the hypothesis has been accepted, which means, there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Table 10: Result of t-test Analysis on the difference between Respondents’ Perceptions about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada

Designation	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Teacher	22	1.70	0.27	0.641	290	0.522	Accepted
Student	270	1.67	0.27				

P-Value of 0.522 > 0.05

The result of a t-test shown in table 10 above was carried out to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada or not. The result shows a significant value of 0.522 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance set as decision rule, consequently, the hypothesis has been accepted. This entailed that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers and students about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja.

Table 11: Result of t-test Analysis on the difference between the Respondents' Perceptions about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja

Designation	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Teacher	22	3.56	0.24	2.694	290	0.007	Rejected
Student	270	3.38	0.31				

P-Value of $0.007 < 0.05$

The analysis in 11 above was carried out to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the extent to which the use of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools is relevant for improving students' understanding of the subject or not. The significant value of 0.007 realized from the analysis is less than 0.05 level of significance set as the decision rule, and the hypothesis stands rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study are quite significant in several ways. Largely, there are substantial areas of its consistency with previous empirical studies, however, each study has its own uniqueness and this (current study) is certainly not an exception. Below are some implications of the findings in relation to other existing studies in literature:

The first finding is that the respondents affirmed the availability of certain instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in their communities such as: settlements, market centres, industrial centres, worship centres, physical features and human resources. This affirmative result of the study is a confirmation of the findings by Dzekoto and Daryl (2018) and Abdulkareem (2016), who in their separate studies also found that certain instructional facilities were available for utilization by teachers to teach their students. Interestingly, all the studies found that most of those resources were largely left unutilized. The main implication here is that there were a number of instructional facilities which the students and teachers affirmed that they are within their reach, and could be utilized for teaching and learning Literature-in-English. Whether these are used or not depends on several other factors which the study also shed light on.

The second finding that the available instructional facilities are utilized sometimes to teach and learn Literature in English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada is not also novel in the light of the findings of other previous studies reviewed. Particularly, Abdirahman, Willy and Mohammed (2018) study found that most of the materials were not adequately utilized which collaborate the current study's finding that the current level of instructional facilities utilization is poor. What this entails is that a valuable means of improving teacher's and students' performance in school (at least in Literature-in-English as a subject) is being ignored. This also entails that the link to maintaining a good relationship between the school and the community is not taken up. The outcome is the circle of poor achievement of students since adequate classroom support that would have improved their understanding of, and performance in the subject is not being properly utilized.

The third finding pertains to extent to which the respondents perceive that the use of instructional facilities for teaching and learning Literature-in-English could be relevant for improving students' understanding of the subject. In line with Abdulkarim's (2016) finding, the use of community tends to better student's understanding and performance in the subject used. In the same vein, Ogah's (2016) indicated that his respondents perceived the use of instructional facilities in the teaching of Literature to be of immense help to students' understanding of drama texts that have related cultural concepts. This implies that community instructional facilities, like most other resources, are relevant teaching resources as far as the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English is concerned. If these have been found to be relevant to a great extent, the implication for teachers is to ensure that the available resources in their communities are not left untapped or unutilized. It would do them (the teachers) and their students a great favour if the resources which have been affirmed to be very relevant for teaching Literature-in-English are adequately utilized, perhaps, the performance of their students in this subject would improve.

This study also confirmed the finding of Dunn's (2009) study in which the respondents perceived that the major setback against effective use of instructional facilities to teach and learn Literature-in-English in secondary schools are: lack

of resources (finance) to support the utilization of the resources that require funding or access fees (as in the case of Dunn's study) and inaccessibility of most of these resources and resources centres. However, the studies (Dunn's and current) also found divergent views especially pertaining to teacher's unwillingness and lack of skills required for effectively utilizing some instructional facilities for the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English. While this is the position of Dunn's (2009) study, in the current study, the respondents disagreed that the inadequate or poor level of utilization of instructional facilities is not attributed to teacher's desire or lack of skills. On the contrary too, the current study found that lack of desire or will toward the utilization of instructional facilities is attributed to school managers, rather than the teachers. It is the poor or total absence of will to support the use of instructional facilities by the school managers that transmit to lack of funding or poor funding for projects or programmes that support the utilization of instructional facilities in schools. Thus, the implication is that, for schools to start utilization the available resources, especially those that require funding (such as inviting a resource person to the school, sponsoring an excursion trip to a museum, workshop, physical feature, etc.) the school managers must support teaching through adequate funding to enable them plan and implement such lofty educational programmes that have great impact on the quality of learning of their students.

The positions (findings) of the current study do not differ significantly with any known previous studies with regard to the findings from the analysis of hypotheses. The respondents who were students and teachers in the sampled schools in Gwagwalada Area Council were unanimous in their opinions regarding all of the areas of investigation. However, the finding from the analysis of hypothesis two indicate that the teachers and the students held significantly, different views regarding the extent of utilization of the available community resources for teaching Literature-in-English in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada. This divergence, however, does not invalidate the general perception that most of the community resources investigated was largely unutilized. The teachers (who had a higher mean) only seem to believe that they were using more of those resources but the fact that their mean is also below 2.50 is a confirmation that they also agreed that the level or extent of utilization was inadequate or poor. Since the level of utilization is confirmed to be poor or low, more efforts should be channeled towards supporting teachers to properly and adequately utilize them to improve their students' understanding and performance in the subject.

Conclusion

Having examined, per students' and teachers' opinions, the relevance of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja, the study concludes that there are many instructional facilities which could be utilized to support the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English in various school communities in the study area. Given the importance of such facilities to the teaching and learning process, it is disappointing that the level of utilization at the time of this study is low, poor or inadequate. The study therefore, concludes that teachers need support to effectively utilize the available instructional facilities to enhance the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English, so as to boost students' understanding and performance in the subject. Accordingly, there are a number of specific recommendations made in the next segment.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings made in this study, and the conclusion drawn above, the following recommendations were made:

1. Although there are several instructional facilities available for teaching Literature-in-English, more should be made accessible to schools so that teachers would be encouraged to utilize them frequently to support the teaching and learning of the subject in schools.
2. More efforts should be made by teachers to utilize instructional facilities to teach their students since they are perceived to be useful. This could be done by training teachers to improve their efficiency in the use of these facilities for teaching Literature-in-English.
3. School managers, government agencies and even non-governmental organizations working in education sector should support teachers with the requisite facilities (funds) to frequently sponsor school trips to resource centres or to invite resource persons from the community to visit the school for the purpose of supporting teaching and learning. This would promote the utilization of instructional facilities for teaching and learning and equally deepen the relationship between the school and the community.
4. Instructional facilities centres where there is access fees should consider making them freely available to schools so as to encourage teachers to frequently use such facilities to promote teaching and learning.

5. In-service training opportunities for teachers should be created to teach teachers how to utilize instructional facilities for teaching and learning since they have been found to be very relevant.

References

- Abdulkarim, U. (2016). Improvisation and use of community resources in Geography teaching in some selected secondary schools of FCT. B. Sc. (Ed) Project, Department of Arts and Social Science Education, University of Abuja.
- Abdirahman Y.H., Willy M. & Mohammed S.S., (2018). The Influence of the Community Involvement on Academic Performance of Secondary Schools: Case of Garowe District. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Researches* Vol. 5, No. 8.
- Dzekoto, G.E. & Daryl B. (2018). Community resource management areas (CREMAs) in Ghana: a promising framework for community-based conservation. UNESDOC Digital Library. Retrieved from: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000368236>
- Jason ectal. (2018). Understanding Difficulties and Resulting Confusion in Learning: *An Integrative Review, Frontier in education journal, Vol. 3*. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2018.00049>
- Kouider M. & Mohamed A.D. (2019). The Major Barriers That Impede the Teaching and Learning of Literature: The Case of the Second Year English LMD Students at the University of Mascara Ichkalat Review ISSN: 2335-1586, University Center of Tamanghasset Algeria
- Ogbuanya, T.C. & Okoye, P.I. (2015). Enhancing Technical and Vocational Education and Training for Poverty Reduction in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.fedau.org>.
- Uchechi, O.B.A. (2021). 'The Role of teaching and learning aids/methods in a changing world'. Retrived from <http://files.ewric.ed.gov>.
- Weipeng Y. & Hui L. (2020). The role of culture in early childhood curriculum development: A case study of curriculum innovations in Hong Kong kindergartens. *Online Sage Journals:comtemporany issues in early childhood*. Retrieved from: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8057-2863>, Vol. 23.